

THE IMPORTANCE OF MUSICAL-DIDACTIC GAMES IN SHAPING THE MUSICAL ABILITIES OF THEIR UPBRINGING IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Annotation: this article will consider the methods of conducting musical-didactic games with the deviation of musical aesthetics and sophistication from traditional activities, giving the pupils of preschool educational organizations knowledge on the basis of innovative ideas.

Keywords: education, regulatory document, educational efficiency, multimedia technology, computers, style, arithmetic operations, environmental impact, presentation, innovation, multimedia, didactics.

In shaping the musical abilities of the pupils of preschool educational organizations, musical didactic games are considered of great importance. The use of musical didactic-games to shape the feeling of aesthetic pleasure in children up to school age will be. It is possible to insist that the musical knowledge given to the child plays a role in his maturation. Musical didactic-games are formed by the ability of those brought up behind to listen to music, to distinguish whether the melodies are sung in low or high verses. They also begin to hiss the harakats corresponding to the rhythmic of what kind of musical oxangs they listen to. Musical didactic-games are of great importance in shaping such abilities in preschool children. Taking into account the fact that not all musical didactic games correspond to the age and mental activity of those brought up, as the limit and norm of all things are, we need to be able to choose musical didactic-games that is, music leaders should be able to reach separately that any games are not suitable for the age and worldview of children. How Didactic-the plot, purpose and rules of the games are different from each other. It is necessary that any games recommended to children have a positive effect on their mental and physical maturation.

Each action and element in the Games is oriented towards a specific goal, having its own purpose and mission. For example, some game is aimed at the child's arm cartilage, while another has the meshes that make up the movement of his legs, in addition, didactic-we can test the resourcefulness, ingenuity and meticulousness of the person brought up through games, which means that we can say that each game has its own purpose and function, and each game requires a

It is necessary to say that at the core of each of the Games is the most important musical education teacher. Today, as a result of the development of technologies, the interest in learning has increased even more, taking lessons and giving knowledge in interactive and corgazmaic methods, with a more original approach to science and a deviation from the traditional course process. In preschool educational organizations, didactic games with a special approach to training through multimedia tools have been providing effective results. 1 musical didactic-through widespread use in games, to the development of the child it has a positive effect, so that we can further enhance the desired qualities. Children up to school age are given to the game, musical Didactic-the desire for musical interests in children

behind games becomes even more obvious, and musical didactic-games are not only a tool for developing a child's abilities for music, but also help to attract schoolchildren brought up in preschool educational organizations to music more widely. To do this, we first need to shape the musical imagination in children, and in them we will have to be able to awaken the musical character. Musical didactic-games help educators to get acquainted with the means of musical expression, musically complex sounds and genres, the form of musical works, the main peculiarity of musical voices. The pedagogical significance of musical didactic-games is such that they open the way for the application of the child's knowledge applied to life. The development of musical abilities in educators deepening the thoughts of educators about musical literacy is one of the main goals of the educator.

Tasks below are set to achieve these goals:

- *Teaching the child to switch to a playing position;*
- *Develop aesthetic sensations, interest in music, love, joy and positive activity;*
- *improving rhythm and tempo sense, dynamic hearing*
- *grow musical memory, shape musical abilities;*
- *further shape the ability to communicate in the game process, be able to hear each other and form friendly relationships.*

In the bloody implementation of such a complex task, children are encouraged to develop musical abilities, children are encouraged to develop their knowledge and skills in all types of musical and artistic works, and we need to be able to correctly choose musical didactic-games for small, medium and large school-preparatory groups. Children learn didactic games mainly through gradual familiarity in music training and develop skills. Music leaders with the rules of the game educate during training introduces and sets specific didactic tasks for them. At first, the music leader will start the game itself, and later the children will be challenged to continue the game of self-independent Holda without the help of an educator. Musical didactic-skills that are ordered through games will later help children complete tasks related to various musical activities without difficulties. Those who are brought up in the process of playing the game not only acquire musical knowledge, but also form their personal qualities, in the first place feelings of friendship and responsibility. Children's it is extremely difficult for us to know to what extent their interest in music is in them in order to shape their musical-emotional abilities. Therefore, it is necessary that the practical part of any game be carried out in two stages:

1. preparation;

2. main story.

At the preparatory stage, children have a common understanding in the totality of all types of musical didactic-games, which is necessary for them to apply different musical sensations in themselves. In this, the games are suitable for drawings, songs and melodies (SAUNTREK), worked into cartoons, become familiar to children and give them special pleasure, making contact with them becomes even more obvious. In the process of musical training, rhythmic movements with children and appropriate dances in the melody use elements as a result of which all training takes place in a playful way. The main task of the music leader in this is to assess the upbringing of their feelings, interests, hobbies, as well as their desire for musical tasks. The development of musical abilities in an individual educator is the main one of the music leader it is the task. What a musical Didactic-the games have four different basic

musical approaches-pitch-low sound,rhythmics,timbre coloring and dynamic colors. We can explain to these in the following way;

Games that develop a child's hearing abilities-allow children to hiss them by listening to music in a loud okhang during the game process.

Games that develop the ability to hiss the rhythmic in a child-educators are the process of playdatural musicwhich allows you to distinguish between sounds and understand their rhythmicity.

Children's games that developingtembri-the hiss of musical timbre in educators creates ways to understand and develop it.

Games that develop signs of dynamics,the ability to pick up and listen to dynamics in children-educators make it possible to understand the music's sharpness and strength,and to hiss,understand, understand the character in music.it is necessary that any game is smoothly fun and consistent.To do this, first of all, the leaders of Misika are required to be active only then the educator will be able to demand activity from children. The implementation of the game in stages provides a more meaningful Organization of the game process.if we carry them out in four stages.

1.At this stage:in the process of musical didactic-playsn,in the main part of it, the child is introduced to the resonant musical repertoire.

2.At this stage:musical didactic-those who are brought up with the rules and composition of the game get acquainted.

3.At this stage:the educators begin to understand the content and rules of order of the didactic-game,its essence and prepare themselves to play independent didactic games.

4.At this stage:the rearing independent ravishta themselves play musical - didactic games.in the process of music training allocated for the academic year, during the course of which the pupils play a variety of musical-didactic games and increase musical skills in narrow training the most important is that the educators learn to carry out the corresponding rhythmic scapes with a full-blooded perception of the music, melodies and songs they hear.

Musical upbringing is the most beautiful, pleasantly comfortable communication between adults and children. Not everyone can always live in harmony with the world of children, this opportunity exists only in educators-educators. Educators dream together with children, plunge into the world of fairy tales, into the world of music, play together with them, dance and create.In the implementation of musical activities in kindergarten, all upbringing is carried out in a interconnected way. Musical works typical of children's age make an unforgettable impression on the little ones.

With the addition of games with musical activity, children's figurative thinking and mastery of figurative memory, movement, skills and skills develop well. It is important for the parallel development of each psychological and pedagogical development.

The play world of children is diverse. In the game chapter, they are very creative. But it is much more difficult to conduct a musical activity in connection with the game. In this case, the educator, relying on the program, will have to act taking into account the age characteristics of the children.

The child reflects his needs and interests in the process of music and play. Taking into account the age and intellectual characteristics of children, the educator must properly provide the room with equipment. Of course, the room should contain musical instruments, musical literature of various types. Because the child must know the history of each musical

instrument, its origin and the directions of sounds in literature. Of great importance in the organization of musical activities is the choice of musical repertoires, the appropriate use of folk games. Folk games have become the most important and component in the life of a child, creating a state of solemnity, joy and joy. Brings up the artistic taste of children. Holidays organized in kindergarten should be a fragment of national holidays. Folk games are also used in this, taking into account the age and developmental characteristics of children.

Music in children's games. Each child is spiritually inclined to different types of music in play exercises. Children themselves learned in training: they dance, sing in "music sessions", "concerts". In such games, the educator divides roles into children, finds different music. Musical-didactic games play a large role in the upbringing of children. Some of them are studied during training. Games develop musical ability, independent and logical thinking. The musical educator reproduces the knowledge acquired in the daily life of children in training, introducing them to new musical-didactic games.

A music educator introduces children to all kinds of musical instruments and switches children around the table where all kinds of musical instruments are placed. Calling the children one by one, asking for the name of the instruments, the tutor playing the music and asking the children which musical instrument he played, etc.

In the process of musical education, listening to music, singing, teaching music literacy, dancing, playing instruments, and giving knowledge such as musical creativity serve as an important tool in all aspects of maturation. The basis of musical upbringing for children is the full-blooded hiss of music: Music leads the child to perfection in every possible way. songs and melodies learned through music-didactic games contribute to the development of musical abilities in children and the growth of the child as a person of a harmonious mature generation. In kindergarten, it will be necessary to teach a conscious understanding of the content and character of songs, melodies studied through each musical-didactic game. Music melodies and songs develop human thinking and consciousness.

Musical-didactic games can also be used when teaching music to children in a small group, taking into account their age characteristics:

Main goal:

Development of musical hearing

To shape the auditory abilities of those brought up through listened melodies and songs.

Functions:

- *To educate the interest of educators in the world of musical and inappropriate sounds, in musical performance;*
- *Development of children's perception of musical and inappropriate sounds;*
- *Growing children's musical experience;*
- *Development of musical and play improvisations in children, the emergence of skills and creative abilities.*

It is possible to organize it as soon as possible in practice for large groups on the example of our game called 'Find A Musical riddle'.

The purpose of the game: to interest children in music through fairy-tale laughter and cartoon music.

Visual weapons: this will require a biga computer, a manitor screen, a colon, and large, small-scale stellar distribution cards.

The course of the game: the Breeders sit with their sutures around the manitor in the form of a crescent moon, the game will consist of 10 or 12 stages yes one stage is at least 3 seconds, and in general the game is 5, which in stages they approach the yucha shown on the screen and find the name of the musical genre and

1. Manitor-on the screen stands the image of dancing multiphilim rhymes about a different genre, standing in a three-way image, and music of a genre belonging to one of these images is played in manitor, and children will have to find a drawing suitable for this music.

The goal of the game (to develop the ability to distinguish musical genres in children).

The team that finds the screen shot corresponding to the song is awarded handout cards.

2. In the next picture, a pace is formed in which at least 3 musical instruments of different appearance are depicted-a voice or music that belongs to one of these 3 instruments is played, the readers are asked about which musical instrument This is.

The goal of the game: to shape the ability to distinguish timbre in children.

3. In the next step , a picture is displayed on the screen with the image of the girls moving up and down, and a sequence of notes rising or falling on the screen is played and asked Which image is suitable for in terms of the musical movement that is playing.

4. The screen depicts the image of cartoon characters in a smiling and sad state. One of the music in the genre of Msjor (cheerful) or minor (sad) sounds children will have to find out which genre is suitable for the hero of the fairy tale.

5. In the next step, several shots of a string group are depicted on the screen, and a picture of any other instrument that does not belong to the string group is depicted inside them. Children will need to find out which instrument does not belong to the group of string instruments.

The purpose of the game: to be able to distinguish the type of musical instruments in children.

6. In the next stage , two pictures are depicted on the screen-in one, the characters of one cartoon character singing, and in the second photo, the characters of two or more cartoon characters singing are depicted-then the children are told to choose a photo corresponding to the singing song.

THE GOAL OF THE GAME:

To shape the ability to distinguish The Voice of polygamy or solo honanda in children.

Through musical didactic games, the musical abilities of preschool children develop, the musical and aesthetic World Vision is enriched, the love of love for music is further enhanced by feelings of collective solidarity and many good qualities are formed

In conclusion, the adoption of such decrees and decisions aimed at ensuring the development of the growing young generation in every possible way as a mature, harmonious person, forming mentally and physically healthy, testifies to how relevant the topic of the dissertation is.

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